

A Review on Role of Big Data Analytics During COVID-19

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Abstract— Coronavirus COVID-19, is a contagious illness triggered by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. It became a pandemic situation leading to lockdown across all nations. This affected the normal lives of people and resulted in economic crisis and decline in populations. Techniques like Big Data Analytics, Machine learning and Deep learning provided the need of the hour solutions to all the sectors including healthcare, manufacturing industries and education. This paper reviews the role of Big Data Analytics, Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques during COVID-19 on healthcare, manufacturing and education sector based on existing research works. It also provides the latest advancement in these techniques and how it is applied in the present world. This review paper summarizes the importance of Big Data Analytics and will help the researchers to make enhanced decisions upon encountering a similar problem in the future.

Keywords— - Big Data Analytics, COVID-19, Education, Healthcare, Manufacturing Industries.

I. BACKGROUND

Corona virus is a contagious disease that can be transmitted from an infected individual to an individual by means of contact and particles released by mouth or nose during coughing, speaking and sneezing. Its effects include respiratory problems ranging from mild to severe conditions and may lead to organ failure and even death. To control the spread of disease, the World Health Organisation and the government across all the nations declared lockdown across the world. This pandemic lockdown affected the crucial aspects of lives of people globally. The people should stay indoors and the infected persons were quarantined to avoid spreading of disease to another person. Compulsory wearing of masks and safety kits were declared.

This lockdown had adverse effects on all the sectors. There was imbalance in food supply chain, disruption in the business and goods supply chain due to restrictions on international trading. Imports and exports were prohibited due to temporary termination of transportation. Tourism sector faced huge loss in the pandemic lockdown due to restriction of movement and social distancing. Also, hospitality value chain which includes leisure parks, hotels, gyms, pools and resorts incurred huge loss. Following tourism and hospitality sector, automobile industries were also severely affected.

Many organisations and companies laid off several workers, thus leading to unemployment in the pandemic. Small- and large-scale industries were affected due to market being shut down. The mental health of the people was also at stake, being refrained from physical connection, lacking social propriety and static environment surrounding them. In overall, it was observed that there was rapid decline in social interactions, an apparent global economic depression and huge burden on healthcare systems of all the nations, being evident that pandemic took a toll globally.

II. INTRODUCTION

It is advancement in technology that provided remedial solution at the immediate hour and connected people virtually across the world during the pandemic lockdown. These latest technologies use enhanced algorithms of Machine learning, Deep learning and Big Data Analytics. These techniques provided optimal solution to many sectors especially on healthcare, manufacturing and educational sector. The significance of these techniques helped many researchers to contribute useful solutions to settle the outbreaks of COVID-19.

A. Big Data:

There are about 147 zettabytes (sextillion bytes) generated per day as of 2024. This amount increased 22.4% from the previous year. An enormous amount of data is generated across the world from various domains. These data are termed as big data. It refers to large sets of complex data comprising of structured, unstructured and semi-structured which aims to reveal hidden patterns in it [1]. Due to this ever-increasing amount of data, there arises a difficulty in manageability and maintenance of these complex heterogeneous interconnected data. The challenge is to store the data collected from multiple sources, integrate them and compute them efficiently.

This huge task is done by Big Data Analytics. It refers to a set of technologies and techniques which involves the process of collecting, organizing, analysing large datasets to reveal hidden patterns and provide useful insights [2]. The characteristics of big data include 4V's namely Volume, Velocity, Variety and Veracity which stands for its huge size, high speed, nature of data and accuracy respectively. Big Data Analytics uses complex analytic techniques to uncover hidden patterns, correlations, and other insights from big data [3].

1) *Need for Big Data in Healthcare:*

There are many electronic devices such as EMR generators, embedders, sensors, sphygmomanometer, wearable devices, pacemakers and diagnostic equipment. These devices generate an enormous amount of data on a day-to-day basis. Also, the data sources may include registration details, biometric information, data from electronic devices, data generated from medical imaging systems such as X-rays, CT scan, patient details, clinical records, and hospital administrative records [4].

To handle these data, there is a requirement of tools that can process the medical data and retrieve immediate solution at time of emergency situation. Therefore, BDA is required and applied to the system which aims to forecast the probability of a patient developing a specific ailment and delivers real-time alerts to medical personnel through ongoing monitoring of the patient's condition. Applying BDA enhances security in the processing of sensitive medical data. This calls for the researchers to extract and discover useful information to the healthcare market. Thus, BDA benefits the healthcare industry by providing better patient care, smarter treatment plan and reduced cost of treatment to the patients.

2) *Need for Big Data on Manufacturing Sectors:*

Manufacturing data are collected from machine sensors, operators' inputs, manufacturing quality systems, ERP and MES systems and many other machine equipment. Big Data Analytics assists manufacturers in understanding their production procedures better, refining their supply chain operations, and enhancing the quality of the final product they deliver. Additionally, it aids manufacturers in forecasting maintenance requirements, mitigating downtime, and fostering a safer workplace environment for their employees. Further, it helps them to strive towards growth and profitability by helping the manufactures to make data-driven decisions, thereby improves operational efficiency by reducing costs and waste.

3) *Need for Big Data in Education:*

Many educational platforms generate data rapidly on a daily basis. These platforms include Learning Management Systems [LMS], Massive Open Online Courses [MOOC], Open Educational Resources [OER] and Learning Object Repository [LOR]. This data includes student data such as student name, registered course, internal and external marks, attendance score and staff data such as staff ID, salary, research papers published and department data and management data records. Applying BDA in this sector, helps teacher to monitor and assess the student performance, analysing the most favoured course among students and helps in introduction of similar favourable courses. This promotes active participation of students and enhances student-teacher relations. It offers better grading system and provides a quick and easy way to handle huge records efficiently.

B. *Machine Learning Techniques:*

Machine learning techniques enable machines to learn and make decisions to solve the given problem statement. Its learning techniques categorises into- supervised learning unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning is the learning based on data which contains a set of outputs for a set of inputs [5]. While unsupervised learning is learning of unlabelled data. Reinforcement learning is employed by an agent to explore the environment and provides reward based on learning from environment and semi-supervised learning lies between supervised and unsupervised learning. These learning techniques consists of enhanced algorithms that can accurately classify and predict the outcome value. Few such algorithms are Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, KNN, Naïve Bayes, etc.

C. *Deep Learning Models:*

These models are trained with large amount of data and complex algorithms that learn and improve overtime, thereby solves complex, real-time problems more accurately. It works based on structure and function of human brain. Machine learning employs neural networks, particularly those with dense layers, to analyse intricate patterns and connections within datasets and this is known as deep learning. Some examples of deep learning algorithms include Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Radical Basis Function Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Autoencoders, and Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs).

III.METHODOLOGY

This work reviews and summarizes the solutions proposed by researchers during COVID-19 in the healthcare, education and manufacturing sector. The paper organises and provides answer to the research question:

- RQ1:** How deep learning and machine learning algorithms have contributed to the healthcare sector at the time of COVID-19?
RQ2: How Big Data Analytics helped manufacturing industries and business corporations to make informed decisions during COVID-19?
RQ3: What are the new or existing technologies that helped students to learn and interact with the teachers during COVID-19 in the education sector?

A proper mechanism is followed for conducting SLR process which starts from collection of research papers, identification of most relevant papers using inclusion and exclusion criteria by creating a predefined collection tailored to particular keywords for searching in the databases such as IEEE Xplore, Elsevier, ScienceDirect and Directory of Open Access Journal.

The aim is to collect research papers related to role of big data, machine learning and deep learning during COVID-19 in the healthcare, education and manufacturing sector. First, all the papers related to COVID-19 are filtered by providing the keywords "COVID-19". by providing the keyword "HEALTHCARE", "EDUCATION", "MANUFACTURING OR BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE", papers related to these are extracted. The different techniques employed in research papers are analysed by reading the abstract.

From those papers, the inclusion and exclusion criteria are set as follows:

- Research paper to be written in English
- Research paper should be published between 2019 and 2023.
- Research topic should be relevant to the research questions.

For assessing the quality of the collected papers, few questions are framed such that the collected papers meet the requirements of the research. The quality assessment questions are:

- Is the aim of the paper clearly stated?
- Does the paper able to provide answer to the research questions under study?
- Did it make a novel contribution during COVID-19?

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Innovations in Healthcare:

Coronavirus is a contagious disease which grows and spreads at an enormous amount. Many patients were affected which led to increase in demand of hospital equipment such as oxygen cylinders, hospital beds, specialized ICU wards, double masks, gloves and PPE kit. Within a short period, all the hospitals in a locality were filled with patients, leaving to shortage of hospital facilities others. The main goal was to prevent the spread of disease and minimize the ill effects of virus on the body of the infected person. The corona virus mutates and grow at an exponential rate, the graph being a logarithmic curve. Fig. 1 illustrates the growth of corona virus each day in all parts of the world.

Fig. 1: Growth of Corona Virus

Karl Pearson coefficient is a mathematical model used to find the relationship between two variables. Computing the Karl Pearson coefficient and applying logistic and linear regression on this curve would help in prediction of growth rate of the virus [6]. Predicting the rate at which the viruses mutate and grow helped in prediction of peak level of spread of the virus. This was done using regression techniques to predict the growth rate and Artificial Neural Networks to classify an area belonging to similar growth rate [7].

To identify whether a person is infected or not, COVID test was introduced. The presence of the virus would result in a COVID positive result. To detect the presence of virus, Artificial Neural Network with five layers was applied which can capture images in X-rays, PET scan, and CT scan and classify them based on learning algorithm employed. Deep Convolutional Neural network was also used for detection of positive test cases using X-rays fed into it [8]. The Deep convolutional neural network consists of complex architecture that recognises image and classify into classes accurately.

In overall, these techniques helped in prediction of peakness of spread of virus, followed by detection of virus and prediction of growth rate of the virus and is illustrated in Fig .2. Thus, these are the major research contributions in the health care sector.

Fig. 2: Techniques used in Healthcare Sector

B. Innovations in Manufacturing Industries:

All the industries were temporarily closed down and no machineries were operated. Production of goods reduced in number and transportation of goods were restricted. To achieve supply chain resilience, a lot of research works were done using questionnaire method and Big Data Analytics techniques. The questionnaire utilized a five-point Likert Scale to inquire about various aspects, including the adoption of Big Data, the alignment of Big Data Analytics (BDA) with supply chain management, purchasing Supply Chain Management Capabilities (PMSC), Internal Risk Management (IRM), and Supply Chain Resilience (SCR). Numerous hypotheses were formulated as part of the research.

The collected data from the questionnaire underwent analysis using partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) and cross-sectional techniques. Additionally, a purposive sampling method was employed in gathering the data. Partial Squares Structural Equation Modelling [PL-SEM] is used to predict and explain target outcomes and works well with smaller samples and optimizes the prediction through multiple iteration [9]. Cross sectional technique is an observational study in which the variables are measured for outcome and exposure at the data, the variables being selected using inclusion and exclusion criteria [10]. Purposive sampling method refers to an iterative process of searching research objects than using a predefined sampling [11].

The measurement model estimation was conducted to evaluate the validity of constructs using discriminant and convergent validity methods. Convergent validity is the degree to which variables or trait are well measured while divergent validity refers to the extent to which measurements of various variables or characteristics are not associated with one another. Construct validity is associated with how adequately a hypothesis psychological construct, as that construct is understood within a given theoretical framework. Along with this, Variance Inflation Factor was done which provides the measure of amount of multicollinearity in regression analysis. The bootstrapping procedure was employed to estimate the hypotheses and analyze the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Content validity is different from construct validity, which refers to degree to which an assessment tool is relevant of targeted construct to be measured.

Figure 3: Techniques used in Manufacturing Sector

Figure 3 illustrates the overall steps performed in the manufacturing sector by Big Data Analytics, Therefore, Big Data Analytics helped in understanding the weakness and strengths in business firm, thereby, providing strategies to strengthen the supply chain resilience to achieve success in e-commerce during the period of COVID-19.

C. Innovations in Education Sector:

During COVID-19, physical classroom interaction among students and teachers was not possible, which posed many challenges in the education industry including regular conduction of examination, commencing classes, effective teaching, enhanced learning and assessment of grades. These challenges were overcome with the help of Big Data Analytics which posed many innovative online education strategies and platforms. Students and teachers connected virtually, learning and examination made online, and even assessment was made online. Big Data Analytics ensures that online education was effective and satisfactory.

Big data is widely applied in adaptive teaching, discovery of teaching rules, and in campus information management.[12] Adaptive learning is a method that provides personalized lessons, practice activities and assessment for individual students by using machine learning and AI techniques. Learning analytics is a method of BDA that analyse data from students and learning environments for better understanding and to enhance learning. This technique helps in assessment of academic progress, prediction of future performance and identification of potential problems. Also, BDA techniques were applied which helps in online decision making and educational data mining [13].

Many innovative ideas were implemented and education platforms have come into force such as Ding Talk, MOOC and LMS. LMS is an application used to administer and document huge records of data which includes videos, courses, workshops, lecture notes, grades and assignments. It offers classroom management, identifies learning gaps using analytical data and reporting methods. MOOC is an open online source aimed in achieving online collaboration to expand higher education and acts as an alternative to formal education method. It offers free resources such as lectures, tests and videos which can be accessed anytime through online platform.

Fig .4: Techniques deployed in Education Sector

Fig.4 depicts the techniques and platforms that were deployed during COVID-19 on the education sector to enable consistent learning to students. ANNOVA and MANOVA techniques were applied to analyse who as access to internet which is the important requirement to resume education during COVID-19. ANNOVA is a statistical analysis used to determine the significance of different variables on a particular outcome. While MANOVA is used in analysis of significance among multiple groups or variables. Based on these techniques, Big Data Analytics were used for student recruitment, improving student performance, teacher and learning effectiveness.[14]

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF METHODOLOGIES USED IN RESEARCH PAPERS

Research Paper	Technique	Description
[15]	Artificial Neural Network Regression Techniques	Build prediction model to analyse the spread of COVID-19 in Indian states. Works on the underlying principle that a state belonging to a particular category have similar spread pattern. Performs research in 3 levels- Exploratory Analysis, modelling of active cases and modelling of peak predictions.
[6]	Logistic and Linear Regression	Forecast the behaviour of COVID-19 diffusion. Uses Wuhan official Dataset. Predicted the number of positive cases using logistic curve.
[16]	Artificial Extreme LSTM Network	Diagnostic system using Ann, ELM and LSTM model used to detection of presence of coronavirus from medical images as input data.
[17]	CRISP-DM, Predictive Modelling	Prediction of spread of COVID-19 using Data Mining techniques, Trimmed decision tress, Stum decision algorithm, Random Forest and KNIME Analytics platform.
[8]	Convolutional Neural Network	Provides solution for faster interpretation of X-ray images to tackle the fast spreading of coronavirus. Developed Cov-AI net system.
[18]	AI, Blockchain and Big Data	An AI-powered system is utilized to enforce social distancing measures, blockchain technology is employed to manage patient records securely, while mathematical modelling and big data analysis are leveraged to track and monitor the spread of the coronavirus.
[9]	PLS-SEM Modelling technique	Focused on restoring and strengthening the supply chain resilience using Big Data Analytics. Potential risks linked to supply chain management were identified through the use of a hypothetical model.
[19]	Cross sectional technique, bootstrapping procedure, purposive sampling method.	Examines the importance of big data management during COVID-19 in Asian economy on the manufacturing sector. It helps in devising strategies after the identification of the weakness and strengths of firms.
[20]	Big data Analysis As a Service	Discusses how Big Data Analytics as a service help small- and large-scale industries to achieve success in e-commerce. Variance inflation factor was assessed, content validity was evaluated.
[21]	Questionnaire based on 5 point Libert Scale	It highlights the impacts of COVID-19 on manufacturing sector from operations management perspective. The results show that the adaptations actions to combat the pandemic situation are repurposing, reconfiguration of work places and reorganisation of work process which revolve around the triangular perspective of organisation, process and technology.
[12]	Big Data Analytics	How big data enabled online education system during COVID-19. Provided feedback, personalization and probability prediction.
[22]	Big Data Analytics	Optimization of learning time, learning methods and learning courses. Focusses the impact of COVID-19 on teacher psychology

V. CONCLUSION

This study mainly concentrated on the evaluation and work of Big Data Analytics during the COVID-19 and the methodologies used in it. It is evident that Big Data Analytics has been the backbone of all the major sectors along with other techniques during the COVID-19 pandemic. It has revolutionized the existing methods into adaptable form for the welfare of the society. This paper focuses on working methodologies of Karl Pearson, artificial neural networks, machine learning and deep learning techniques. This proposed agenda includes the importance of understanding the role of big data in determining the trends and patterns for predictions and building a good foundation and business.

The paper can be further reviewed for use for Big Data Analytics on other sectors like social media, tourism, IT companies, etc. How Big Data Analytics helped in those sectors during COVID-19 pandemic. The paper can be further enhanced to analyse various other techniques applied in the healthcare, manufacturing, education and other sectors. The paper can be further reviewed with integration of Big Data Analytics with machine learning, cloud, blockchain, etc. Thus, the big data played a vital role in various sectors during the COVID-19 pandemic and was very much useful for the development of public welfare in safety segments.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bi Z, Cochran D. Big data analytics with applications. *J Manag Anal.* 2014;1(4):249–65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23270012.2014.992985>.
- [2]. Carter P. Big data analytics: future architectures, skills and roadmaps for the CIO: in white paper, IDC sponsored by SAS. 2011. p. 1–16.
- [3]. Md. Saifur Rahman, Hassan Reza A *Systematic Review Towards Big Data Analytics in Social Media*. Big Data Mining and Analytics Volume 5, Number 3, September 2022 DOI: 10.26599/BDMA.2022.9020009
- [4]. Kornelia Batko ,Andrzej Ślęzak. *The use of Big Data Analytics in healthcare*. Journal of Big Data volume 9, Article number: 3 (2022).
- [5]. David Mhlanga. *The Role of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: What Lessons Are We Learning on 4IR and the Sustainable Development Goals*. 2022 Feb 8;19(3):1879. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph19031879.
- [6]. Davide Tosi, DPhil, Alessandro Campi, DPhil. *How Data Analytics and Big Data Can Help Scientists in Managing COVID-19 Diffusion: Modeling Study to Predict the COVID-19 Diffusion in Italy and the Lombardy Region*. (J Med Internet Res 2020;22(10):e21081) doi: 10.2196/21081.
- [7]. Anupam Prakash, Piyush Sharma, Indrajeet Kumar Sinha, Upendra Pratap Singh. *Spread & Peak Prediction of Covid-19 using ANN and Regression*. October 2020 DOI: 10.1109/BigMM50055.2020.00062.
- [8]. Mohit Mishra, Varun Parashar, Rushikesh Shimpi. *Development and evaluation of an AI System for early detection of Covid-19 pneumonia using X-ray (Student Consortium)*. 2020 IEEE Sixth International Conference on Multimedia Big Data (BigMM). DOI: 10.1109/BigMM50055.2020.00051.
- [9]. Pavitra Dhamija, Donald, Sunil Luthra, Surajit Bag. *How big data analytics can help manufacturing companies strengthen supply chain resilience in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic*. Journal of logistic management DOI:10.1108/IJLM-02-2021-0095.
- [10]. Maninder Singh Setia. *Methodology Series Module 3: Cross-sectional Studies*. Indian J Dermatol. 2016 May-Jun; 61(3): 261–264. doi: 10.4103/0019-5154.182410
- [11]. Joseph Hair, Abdullah Alamer. *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in second language and education research: Guidelines using an applied example*. Research Methods in Applied Linguistics Volume 1, Issue 3, December 2022, 100027.
- [12]. Yuhuan Cuia, Zezhong Maa, Liya Wang, Aimin Yang, Qiumei Liua, Shanshan Konga, Huifang Wang. *A survey on big data-enabled innovative online education systems during the COVID-19 pandemic*. Journal of Innovation & Knowledge DOI:10.1016/j.jik.2022.100295.
- [13]. Sarita Verma, Mamta, Deepika Verma. *The Role of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence for Impact on Education during Covid-19*. Volume 1, Issue 2; March 2021 ISSN: 2582-8118.
- [14]. Faisal Syafar, Halimah Husain, Edy Sabara. *The Role of Big Data Quality and Information Analytics in Indonesia Higher Education Sector during Covid-19 Pandemic* International Journal of New Technology and Research (IJNTR) ISSN: 2454-4116, Volume-6, Issue-9, September 2020 Pages 29-33.
- [15]. Anupam Prakash, Piyush Sharma, Indrajeet Kumar Sinha, Upendra Pratap Singh. *Spread & Peak Prediction of Covid-19 using ANN and Regression*. October 2020 DOI: 10.1109/BigMM50055.2020.00062.
- [16]. Mohammad Jamshidi; Ali Lalbakhsh; Jakub Talla; Zdeněk Peroutka; Farimah Hadjilooei; Pedram Lalbakhsh; Morteza Jamshidi; Luigi La Spada; Mirhamed Mirmozafari; Mojgan Dehghani; Asal Sabet; Saeed Roshani; Sobhan Roshani; Nima Bayat-Makou; Bahare Mohamadzade; Zahra Malek; Alireza Jamshidi; Sarah Kiani; Hamed Hashemi-Dezaki; Wahab Mohyuddin. *Artificial Intelligence and COVID-19: Deep Learning Approaches for Diagnosis and Treatment*. Volume: DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3001973
- [17]. Muhammad Akbar Rivai, Sfenrianto. *Analysis of Corona Virus spread uses the CRISP-DM as a Framework: Predictive Modelling*. Volume 9, No.3, May - June 2020 <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijatce/2020/76932020>.
- [18]. Shiva Ahir, Dipali Telavane, Riya Thomas. *The impact of Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Big Data and evolving technologies in Coronavirus Disease - 2019 (COVID-19) curtailment*. 2020 International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC). DOI: 10.1109/ICOSEC49089.2020.9215294.
- [19]. Junling Zhang, Hualong L. *The Impact of Big Data Management Capabilities on the Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Asian Economy During COVID-19: The Mediating Role of Organizational Agility and Moderating Role of Information Technology Capability*. Information technology. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.833026.
- [20]. Pham Quang Huy, and Vu Kien Phuc *Big data in relation with business intelligence capabilities and e-commerce during COVID-19 pandemic in accountant's perspective*. Future business journal, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00221-4>
- [21]. Surajit Bag, Pavitra Dhamija, Sunil Luthra, Donald Huisingh. *How big data analytics can help manufacturing companies strengthen supply chain resilience in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic*. June 2023, ISSN: 0957-4093.
- [22]. Jia Li, Yuhong Jiang. *The Research Trend of Big Data in Education and the Impact of Teacher Psychology on Educational Development During COVID-19: A Systematic Review and Future Perspective*. 2021 Oct 27. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.753388.
- [23]. Wallace J. Hopp, Jun Li, Guihua Wang. *Big Data and the Precision Medicine Revolution*. Production and Operations Management Society Vol. 27, No. 9, September 2018, pp. 1647–1664.
- [24]. Laraib Aslam Haafza, Mazhar Javed Awan, Adnan Abid, Awais Yasin, Haitham Nobanee and Muhammad Shoaib Farooq. *Big Data COVID-19 Systematic Literature Review: Pandemic Crisis*. Electronics 2021, 10, 3125.
- [25]. Hafsa Bureen Syeda, Mahanazuddin Syed, Kevin Wayne Sexton, Shorabuddin Syed, Salma Begum, Farhanuddin Syed, Fred Prior, Feliciano Yu. *Role of Machine Learning Techniques to Tackle the COVID-19 Crisis: Systematic Review*. 2021 Jan 11. DOI: 10.2196/23811.
- [26]. Asmat Ara Shaikh, Anuj Kumar, Kruti Jani, Saloni Mitra, Diego A. García-Tadeo, Agilandeswari, Devarajan. *The Role of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence for making a Digital Classroom and its sustainable Impact on Education during Covid-19*. Design and Materials (ICDM)-2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.09.368>.
- [27]. Zainab Abbas Abdulhussein Alwaeli, Abdullahi Abdu Ibrahim. *Predicting Covid-19 Trajectory Using Machine Learning*. 2020 4th International Symposium on Multidisciplinary Studies and Innovative Technologies (ISMSIT). DOI: 10.1109/ISMSIT50672.2020.9255149.
- [28]. Liu, Qia, Huang, Zhenzhenb. *Research on intelligent prevention and control of COVID-19 in China's urban rail transit based on artificial intelligence and big data*. Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 9085-9090, 2020. DOI: 10.3233/JIFS-189307
- [29] Xue, F.; Li, X.; Zhang, T.; Hu, N. *Stock market reactions to the COVID-19 pandemic: The moderating role of corporate big data strategies based on Word2Vec*. Pac. Basin Financ. J. 2021, 68, 101608.
- [30]. Campbell MC, Inman JJ, Kirmani A, Price LL (2020) In times of trouble: a framework for understanding consumers' responses to threats. *J Consum Res* 47(3):311–326. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucaa036>
- [31]. Nofiani D, Indarti N, Lukito-Budi AS, Manik HFGG (2021) *The dynamics between balanced and combined ambidextrous strategies: a paradoxical affair about the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on SMEs' performance*. *J Entrep Emerg Econ* 13(5):1262–1286
- [32]. Bressan A, Duarte Alonso A, Kok SK (2021) *Confronting the unprece- dented: micro and small businesses in the age of COVID-19*. *Int J Entrep Behav Res* 27(3):799–820. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-09-2020-0602>
- [33]. Kitukutha NM, Vasa L, Oláh J (2021) *The impact of COVID-19 on the economy and sustainable e-commerce*. *Forum Scientiae Oeconomia* 9(2):47–72
- [34]. Alwan SY, Hu Y, Al Asbahi AAMH, Al Harazi YK, Al Harazi AK (2023) *Sustainable and resilient e-commerce under COVID-19 pandemic: a hybrid grey decision-making approach*. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 30:47328–47348. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-25456-0>.
- [35]. Erverson B. G. de Sousa, Bruno Alexandre, Rafael Ferreira Mello, Taciana, Pontual Falcão, Boban Vesin, Dragan Gašević *Applications of Learning Analytics in High Schools: A Systematic Literature Review*. Volume 4 - 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2021.737>.
- [36]. Helen Onyeaka, Christian K Anumudu, Zainab T Al-Sharif, Esther Egele-Godswill, Paul Mbaegbu. *COVID-19 pandemic: A review of the global lockdown and its far-reaching effects*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00368504211019854>.
- [37]. Ogbolosingha AJ, Singh A. COVID-19 pandemic: review of impediments to public health measures in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Am J Prevent Med Pub Health* 2020; 6(3): 68–75.
- [38]. Fakhruddin BS, Blanchard K, Ragupathy D. Are we there yet? The transition from response to recovery for the COVID-19 pandemic. *Progr Disaster Sci* 2020; 7: 100102.

- [39]. Al-Sharif ZT, Nussrat HH, Al-Najjar SZ, et al. The emergence of COVID-19 and its pandemic potential as a global health security threat and its effect on future life strategy. *System Rev Pharm* 2021; 12(3): 259–269.
- [40]. Hulley SB, Cummings SR, Browner WS, Grady D, Hearst N, Newman TB. *Designing Clinical Research*. 2nd ed. Philadelphia, USA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2001.
- [41]. Boerma T, Requejo J, Victora CG, Amouzou A, Asha G, Agyepong I, Borghi J. Countdown to 2030: tracking progress towards universal coverage for reproductive, maternal, newborn, and child health. *Lancet*. 2018;391(10129):1538–48.
- [42]. Bollier D, Firestone CM. *The promise and peril of big data*. Washington, D.C: Aspen Institute, Communications and Society Program; 2010. p. 1–66.